

Deliverable D7.2
First report on setup of CoE governing bodies,
infrastructure, KPI defs, IPR implementation

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D7.2 First report on setup of CoE governing bodies, infrastructure, KPI definitions, IPR implementation

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1 Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1 summarises the governing bodies, the management structures and procedures, the service catalogue, the communication plan and a first draft of the KPIs.

It includes the implementation (i) of an effective MaX governance structure, and support to the governing boards, (ii) of a target- and result-oriented, efficient management structure of MaX; regarding also the management of risk and IP issues, and (iii) of infrastructure services for MaX activities. An effective internal and external communication was planned.

Parts of chapters 2, 3 and 5 are required by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

2 First report on setup of MaX governing bodies

MaX is guided by an **Executive Board (EB)**, the key decision-making body (also named General Assembly (GA) in the Grant Agreement), and by a **Director**, the project coordinator. They coordinate the actions of the WPs towards common objectives, monitor the development of the activities and the interactions with users, analyse any difficulties / new opportunities in the CoE development, and determine the necessary actions. They prepare the required MaX activity reports to the European Commission.

The **Executive Board** is defined to include the PIs of all nodes. It also includes all WP leaders, with the exception of WP7, and is chaired by the Director. The members of the Executive Board, all having the right to vote, are: Elisa Molinari (MaX Director), CNR Nano; Stefano Baroni, SISSA; Pablo Ordejón, ICN2; Stefan Blügel, Jülich; Nicola Marzari, EPFL; Carlo Cavazzoni, CINECA; José Maria Cela, BSC; Thomas Schulthess, ETH Zurich; Erwin Laure, KTH; Piero Altoè, E4; Carlo Daffara, CloudWeavers; Ivan Girotto, UNESCO. The leader of WP7 and the Executive Manager also participate to EB meetings without voting rights. A formal meeting of the EB was convened during the kick-off meeting held in Modena in December 2015. Additional informal meetings of the EB were held by teleconference.

The individual **WP leaders** coordinate the activities of their WPs, make sure that these proceed smoothly, and report the main achievements as well as any major difficulty or new opportunity to the Director and the EB. To this end, the WP leaders monitor and harmonise the activities of the Task leaders within their WP. The WP leaders are also in charge of producing the respective input for the EB, as needed to complete the activity reports for the European Commission. The WPs and the respective leading names and institutions are: WP1 – Stefano Baroni – SISSA, WP2 – Pablo Ordejón – ICN2, WP3 – Nicola Marzari – EPFL, WP4 – Carlo Cavazzoni – CINECA, WP5 – Carlo Daffara – Cloudweavers, WP6 – Stefan Blügel – Jülich, WP7 – Andrea Ferretti – CNR.

An **International Advisory Board (IAB)**, also named External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) in the Grant Agreement, is established to advise the Director and the EB on the main strategic choices that may be needed during the duration of MaX, to evaluate the overall progress with respect to the objectives, and to help shaping the evolution of MaX after the end of the project. The IAB will be composed of leading experts from academia and industry

worldwide; thus, it will also provide a useful window on frontier developments outside MaX. The IAB will comprise a subcommittee, the Industrial Advisory Group (IAG), established to offer specific advice on industrial needs and on appropriate strategies and approaches. The composition is currently being finalized. Alessandro Curioni (Head of the IBM Research-Zurich Lab and IBM-Europe Vice-President) and Marie-Christine Sawley (Intel Director of the Exascale Lab Europe in Paris) have accepted to join.

The overall structure of MaX governance and organization structure is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: MaX governance and organization

3 First report on setup of MaX management

Setting up MaX as an infrastructure is a key task, which will develop throughout month 30 and includes organizing effective management, services, and procedures, and communication. Months 1-6 have seen the definition and set-up of MaX management: its main features are described in this chapter.

3.1 MaX managing team

MaX management is ensured by WP7, led by CNR with the collaboration of all nodes. A central role is played by the MaX managing team (Executive manager and staff), who ensures the implementation of the goals defined by the EB and Director, manages service access and offers a single and easy entry point to the users as illustrated in Fig.1.

As a first step for MaX implementation, the managing team was set up. MaX Executive Manager is Dr. Guido Chiarotti, with dual background: in computational physics and materials science, as well as in the management of IT companies.

The managing team also includes Dr. Nadja Sändig, MaX Technical Secretariat; Luisa Neri, communication activities; Maddalena Scandola, press office; Anna Grazia Stefani and Paola Corezzola, administration. Further contributions to the management support team come from the staff of CNR or other units.

3.2 Management objectives and principles

The main **objectives** of the management action are:

- To steer, coordinate and manage the project implementation in close coordination with the EC;
- To foster the effective cooperation and integration of the teams and activities;
- To manage and control schedule, resources and quality;
- To ensure the financial, legal and administrative project management;
- To ensure the knowledge and data management of the project;
- To define standards, tools and procedures for the internal communication;
- To manage ethical and gender issues related to the project.
- To coordinate with the ecosystem of e-infrastructures, especially the other CoEs.

The **principles** inspiring MaX management are:

- focus on user/business/development needs,
- deliver on time,
- collaborate with partners, industry and users,
- attention on quality,
- build up incrementally,
- develop iteratively, and
- communicate continuously and clearly.

The management will focus on people, interaction, community, skills, and talents.

These principles coincide in part with those of the ‘Dynamic System Development Method’ (DSDM) and in part with those of ‘Crystal’, both methodologies of the ‘Agile’ development style. For this reason, MaX management actions will be inspired to both DSDM and Crystal. However it should not be intended that such methodologies are adopted or followed by MaX management in a strict or formal way.

Risk management will be an integral part of the project lifecycle to minimize possible deviations from the expected results and schedule. Risk management will involve the following players:

- (i) The Coordinator and the WP Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for risk identification and management.

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- (ii) Decision making related to major risks and challenges is responsibility of the General Assembly.
- (iii) WPLs are responsible for risk analysis, controlling, tracking and for the implementation of remedial and preventive actions within their WPs.
- (iv) Task Leaders and performers are responsible for risk identification, communication and documentation within their tasks.

Specific risks and contingency plans are defined for each WP are presented and discussed in the grant agreement. Based on that information, the principal factors can be summarized in the following SWOT diagram:

	HELPFUL	HARMFUL
INTERNAL	<p>Strengths due to MAX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capability to manage shared data and workflows • Capability to develop and validate new technologies • Capability to manage IPR • Wide coverage of IT skills • Co-design Capabilities • Flexible Service Offer • Large users base of flagship codes 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in s/w implementation (WP1, WP3, WP5) • Codes too entangled for modularization (WP1, WP4) • Limited time span of MaX project (WP5, WP6) • Underestimation of workload (all WPs)
EXTERNAL	<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New emerging technologies (WP1, WP3, WP4) • Excess of users response (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6) • Resolution of bugs emerging in HTC (WP3) and HPC (WP1, WP4) • New emerging co-design strategies (WP4) • New emerging HPC architectures (WP1, WP3, WP4) 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unexpected emerging standards (WP1, WP3, WP4) • Lack on users response (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6) • Reticence of industries (WP2, WP3, WP5) • Licence restriction due to platforms (WP4) • Availability of co-design H/W (WP4) • End-users limited interest in training and industrial services (WP5, WP6)

3.3 Management activities

The following paragraphs list the main activities performed by the management in order to support the MaX director and governing bodies.

Governance, Monitoring and Quality Assurance

- Day-to-day coordination of the project in order to reinforce interrelations among the WPs and make sure all deadlines are met while delivering quality research;
- Coordination of work plan execution with respect to the aimed quality and effectiveness of the methodologies deployed in the work-packages to ensure that the project works as an integrated whole;

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- Risk and quality assurance management to monitor continuously the progress of the project and its alignment with the initial objectives in order to apply preventive/corrective actions when necessary;
- Monitoring any changes to the project, methods, approaches and evolution of the consortium that may alter the planning, and proposing appropriate actions whenever appropriate (subject to the agreement/discussion with the EC).
- Support to the Coordinator and Governing bodies (incl. meetings, information flow with the EC)
- Assessment of deliverables by internal/external peer review process.
- Delivery of periodic reports required by the European Commission.
- Monitoring and elaborating necessary information related to policy making.
- Consortium meetings: Regular meetings at project level are necessary “tools” for a common understanding and successful collaboration. Cross-WP meetings: regular monthly teleconferences will be organised among all WP leaders in order to discuss the progress of the work, the quality of deliveries or any updates to be considered in the work plan.

Administrative, legal and financial management

- Overall legal, financial and administrative management.
- Day-to-day management and project secretariat activities.
- Manage the access rights and the communications via the EU electronic exchange system.
- Helpdesk providing assistance to the administrative staff of the partners in complying with reporting rules/schedules.
- Designing and maintaining specific working templates for activity monitoring/assessment/reporting.
- Budget and reporting: managing and monitoring with respect to the contractual obligations and the activities to be performed.
- Management and distribution of the EU financial contribution.
- Maintaining and updating the consortium agreement and third parties management.
- Organization and management of regular call conferences for monitoring/planning and of project meetings (prepare and distribute agendas, working papers, minutes and reports together with the follow-up actions).

Knowledge and communication management

- Set-up of a collaborative platform and repository for knowledge management to facilitate the secure and updated exchange of larger project information (reports, simulations, data, etc.).
- Establishment and management of communication procedures and tools to facilitate exchange among partners (internal communication) and with interested entities outside the consortium (external communication).
- Design, implement, and update the Data Management Plan.

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- Content management and maintenance of web-based project management tools/ platform/ repositories.
- Communications within the ecosystem, and direct interactions with other components of the e-infrastructure ecosystem

3.4 Setup of basic management tools

The management tools available in the market were identified and compared, taking into account the above principles and the relatively small scale of MaX operations. Several options were initially selected to optimize the communication between the partners and external persons. A particular attention was attached to the compatibility with the communication & management tools of the other CoEs.

As a result of the above-mentioned process, MaX involves a combination of classical and innovative management. Web-based tools typical of virtual research environments (VRE) are adopted for internal and external management. A social communication intranet, based on the Google apps, was implemented. Among the apps, the most used are Google Mail, Google Drive, Google Site, Google Groups, Google Calendar, Google Hangout and Google+ social suite. An e-mail-based Customers Relationship Management (CRM) suite (similar to Streak) is adopted for tracking all the activities explicitly directed toward users and customers. The apps thus include a knowledge management database, socials, chats, teleconference calls, forum activities, CRM, and blogs. Moreover all the apps can be easily personalized and include a (script-base) process suite that was implemented along with the use and project advancements, consistently with the ‘build up incrementally’ and ‘develop iteratively’ management principles.

3.5 Coordination and networking within e-infrastructures, HPC and domain ecosystem

MaX operates in a rather complex ecosystem of European initiatives, both EC- and community-driven. Establishing and fostering productive relations with such system is a key endeavour in view of the CoE mission. The first six months have seen the active participation of MaX in a broad number of events and collaborative meetings, resulting in several coordination initiatives. The management has ensured such activity as well as the sharing of its results.

Concerning the *e-infrastructure ecosystem*, the general strategy events held in Roma on September 29-30, 2015 (EXDCI, PRACE and ETP4HPC) and in Brussels on November 9, 2015, have seen an active role of several MaX representatives, including the Director, and offered opportunities for several informal meetings. Useful interactions with the ETP4HPC were stimulated with MaX participation in the cPPP Partnership Board Meeting, organized by the EC in Brussels on November 10, 2015.

In addition, direct interactions have been established with *the other CoEs* whose domain is most closely related to MaX, with discussions and plans for some joint activities. Among the face-to-face meetings held so far, we mention those:

- with Nomad and E-Cam in Lugano (September 16-18, 2016) and in Lausanne (December 11, 2015)
 - with Nomad in San Sebastian (September 10, 2015)
 - with BioExcel (whose Director is also a PI of MaX) in Brussels on November 10, 2015.
- We also had extended technical discussions with POP CoE, and actively participated in the kick-off meeting of EoCoE in Paris (October 30, 2015).

Networking within the *main reference community of quantum computational materials science* continued systematically through many conferences attended by MaX members. Here we just mention the big *Psi-k -2015* Conference held in San Sebastian, Spain, from September 6 to 10, just after the start of MaX. The Conference, convening the European electronic structure community every 5th year, involved this time over 1500 participants with several invited technical presentations by MaX teams. MaX was introduced in a plenary talk by MaX Director, who illustrated the strategy and the opportunities that the CoE will offer to users from that community, and in many informal discussion throughout the meeting. At the same time, *networking within the international HPC community* further developed through workshop and meetings with dedicated presentations by MaX members, e.g. at SuperComputing15 (Austin, Texas, November 15-20), ICT2015 (Lisbon, October 20-22, 2015), DFT4exascale (Berkeley, October 2, 2015), and MHPC meeting (Trieste, February 25-26, 2016).

Networking with the Graphene Flagship and the European Materials Modelling Council was just started with individual MaX members participating in several workshops and meeting. It will continue in the next future with more structured interactions.

3.6 Kick-off meeting

A first informal meeting of the MaX consortium was held just after communication of approval by the EC to start planning. A 2-day Kick-Off meeting was then held in Modena, Italy on December 14-15, 2015, organized by CNR with active participation of all MaX partner groups including younger researchers and a few PhD students (64 persons in total). The meeting included a general presentation of the CoE, a detailed discussion of the individual WPs, with emphasis on industry-oriented tasks, and room for dedicated discussions on specific activities.

4 Services

4.1 Catalogue of services

The development, consolidation and evolution of a Catalogue of Services is central to MaX initiative. In the original proposal a number of possible services were already listed, together with some provisioning policies. These are reported in Table 1.

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	service	main WPs	target users			
			governments, regions (*), public institutions	large projects, large scale infrastructures	large industries	SMEs, small research groups
custom development	customized workflows aimed at solving scientific problems	WP2, WP3	x	xxx	xxx	xxx
	new or optimized functionalities for a specific problem	WP1, WP2	x	xxx	xxx	xxx
	new I/O formats to support different pre and post processing	WP1, WP3	x	xxx	xx	x
	new user interfaces to cope with a specific class of users	WP1, WP3	x	xxx	xx	xx
	integration of components/modules with other suites of codes	WP3	xx	xxx	xx	x
	computational materials science: general consulting	WP1- WP3	xx	xx	xxx	x
	on demand implementation of specific features	WP1	x	xxx	xxx	xxx
	optimization and porting issues	WP1	xx	xxx	xx	x
	enabling on high-end HPC systems and new architectures	WP4	xx	xxx	x	x
	efficient use of HPC resources, scaling etc	WP4	x	xx	xxx	x
consulting	scientific case, model and workflows	WP2	xx	xx	xxx	xx
	definition of workflows for specific properties	WP2, WP3	xx	xxx	xxx	xx
	definition of workflows for specific codes	WP1, WP3	x	xxx	xxx	xxx
	electronic structure data analysis and processing	WP1, WP3	x	xx	xxx	x
	support to users in applications for HPC resources	WP5	xx	xxx	xx	xxx
	'tiger team' on site audit	WP5 and all	xx	xxx	xxx	x
	quality certifications (electronic structure codes and HPC)	WP2	x	xx	xxx	xxx
	helpdesk and support on the codes themselves	WP5	xxx	xxx	xxx	xx
	helpdesk and support on specific simulation and execution issues	WP5	xx	xxx	xx	x
	bug triaging, fixing and management	WP5	x	xxx	xxx	x
training	on-site support	WP5	xx	xxx	xxx	x
	training of industrial researchers in MaX laboratories	WP6	x	xx	xxx	xx
	custom training courses or modules, possibly held on site	WP6	xxx	xxx	xx	x
	visiting / access to MaX laboratories	WP6	xxx	xx	xx	xx
	'ad-hoc webinars	WP6	xx	xxx	xxx	xx

(*) regions may be especially interested in funding actions towards industries, especially SMEs

Table 1: Catalogue of some of the possible services envisaged in MaX proposal. Different categories are included, e.g., custom development projects, consulting, helpdesk support, and training.

Most of the services provided by MaX are intended to support and facilitate the use of MaX flagship codes in order to:

- Shorten time to deliver scientific cases.
- Reduce time to market in the innovation processes involving computer-assisted materials design.
- Optimize available (public) resources utilisation.
- Increase the user-base, both academic and industrial.

Central in MaX services delivering is the presence of a Single User Entry Point (SUEP) directly accessible from the MaX web platform, or via email, from which all MaX services can be activated or requested.

4.2 Service provisioning and access policies

Provisioning of the services provided by MAX belongs to three different classes:

- Forum-like (basic) support
- Trouble Tickets System (TTS) support
- Custom development and Consulting

Together with these support services, and in line with the SUEP provisioning philosophy, MaX will also provide a unique access point service for code downloading and documentation. The details of this service delivering will be defined within month 12.

The access policy to different services will be decided case by case, depending on the specific service. Access to software-related forums or blogs will be in general provided free of charge, upon subscription. The TTS based services will be typically provided upon payment, or delivered to specific classes of users (for example PRACE users) upon agreement with the entities to which these users belongs. Direct service provisioning will be provided upon contracts between the interested third party and one of the MaX partners (see below the guidelines for engagement).

4.3 Service development

In the first 6 months of the MaX Centre, a number of meetings of the Management Team, WP Leaders and PIs have focused on the design of the services to be provisioned by the Centre.

As an example of the services under development, in the following we will briefly describe the structure of the MaX helpdesk service, part of the TTS class.

MaX helpdesk is organized as a two level support service with single user entry point. The HPC Centres part of the MaX consortium will operate the first level, while the second level will be handled by the Scientific Partners.

The support is intended to increase the user base of the MaX Flagship codes (YAMBO, SIESTA, QUANTUM ESPRESSO, FLEUR, and AiiDA), by (a) introducing non-experts to the use of the codes and (b) facilitating the code usage. MaX will assist the potential code users in:

- Code utilisation, with particular attention on optimal - HPC focussed - use and performance;
- Input preparation and output interpretation;
- Implementation of small code modification upon request;
- Development of technical/scientific aspects (code-related) of national, European and international proposals;
- Choosing the appropriate software in respect to the research context;
- Analysing the scalability properties of the codes;

- Establishing the adequacy of requested CPU time.

Overall, the service is envisioned to be restricted to TTS- habilitated users, but all procedures may be further restricted to specific subsets of subscribers (such as PRACE applicants or awardees). The answers provided to the users will be tentatively organised in the way to be re-usable for the construction of a knowledge base directly accessible by the code community.

After being subject to the approval of the General Assembly and agreed on by all the partners, this service will be open to End Users in beta form by Month 8 (April 2016) and provisioned in final form by Month 12.

4.4 Contractor relationship

Execution of third party orders are regulated by the “Guidelines for engagement to execute a third party order”, is attached as Annex I. These guidelines have been adopted to ensure prompt response and high quality execution to MaX premium customers.

A more detailed report on the for-pay services will be provided in the context of the business plan at month 12.

5 Communication plan

MaX is a user-focused, problem-oriented Center of Excellence supporting the needs and vision of a number of players on HPC-oriented materials simulations. Crucial for general purpose communication is the concept of materials combined with innovation and computer-design. This should be complemented by the concept of challenge associated to the exascale-transition.

5.1 Communication goals

- To develop a unified and coherent MaX image.
- To communicate MaX strategy and goals.
- To enhance community identity among MaX stakeholders.
- To promote MaX services, especially industry-oriented services.
- To communicate major MaX milestone achievements.
- To prepare the communication for the “next big step” (CoE evolution).

5.2 Target segmentation and key messages

MAX’s reference community is essentially a scientific community. The complex network of interactions between community members and the external persons can be represented by concentric circles with decreasing levels of specialization (along the lines of Google+ circles): communication is different in different circles, both in terms of communication dynamics and communication styles & channels.

To better define the circle-dependent communication styles, we have adopted the following communication keywords in the different circles:

Circle-1 DEVELOPERS - Communication Keyword: TECH-EXPERT

Circle-2 DOMAIN SCIENTIST - Communication Keyword: EXCELLENCE

Circle-3 END-USERS and STAKEHOLDERS - Communication Keyword: TOP-NOTCH

Circle-4 SCIENCE INTERESTED PERSONS - Communication Keyword: DISCOVERY

Circle-5 CITIZENS - Communication Keyword: FUTURE

These communication keywords are used as a mental guide in designing the communication strategy and shared particularly with external collaborators like graphics designers, journalists, public relations or marketing communication consultants, etc. The communication dynamics of the different circles will be better clarified in the section discussing the communication channels.

Key messages / payoffs for the above circles are summarized below:

Generalist Payoff: it includes both, the MaX vision and its mission. To cope with the complexity of the present society it should also be “open” and more oriented towards middle layer reference circles (*stakeholders* and *science interested persons*). Suggested payoff/message: “*What if materials simulations were 1000x faster and more workable? Driving the exascale transition.*”

Circle-1 and 2 (developers + domain scientists) key-message: Data: provenance, reliability and sharing; Exabyte, Infrastructure, Programs Development, Maintenance, Performances, Exaflops, Best practices, Co-design, Community Codes, Reliability, Domain specific libraries, data locality, “*MaX Centre of Excellence: an e-infrastructure on materials simulation aimed at enhancing community-code developments and maintenance, hardware HPC co-design, intelligent data analytics for improved workability. To actively drive the exascale transition*”.

Circle-3 (end-users and stakeholders) key-message: Usability, Platforms, Ecosystem of applications, Workflow, Data storage, Data analysis, Performances. “*Building an ecosystem of capabilities and applications to innovate material discovery*”.

Circle-4 (science interested persons) key-message: Material discovery, research-oriented technology, “*MaX: a research-oriented technology to innovate and speed up material discovery*”, “*Innovating material discovery by computer-assisted material design*”.

Circle-5 (citizens) key-message: New Materials, Innovation, Challenge, Computer-Design, “*Designing the materials of the future*”, “*Transforming the way new materials are thought*”, “*No new materials, no innovation*”.

5.3 Communication channels

Traditional-media communications

Traditional-media communications outlets will be used by MaX through its partners' press offices and their networks. This channel is activated to promote specific MaX events or milestone achievements to communicate MaX strategy, ambitions and policy.

Web presence

MaX web presence is set out on two different web sites: the first targeted to all the reference circles and designed to communicate mostly the MaX identity (visible at www.max-center.eu); the second intended to communicate mostly MaX industry-oriented services targeted on the third circle (science interested persons and entrepreneurs). The two web sites should be seen as the two sides of the same coin: this should be evident from the graphical features and the communication style and general design. The deliverables D5.1 (month 6) and D7.1 (month 4) describe the websites.

Social-media presence

Due to their intrinsically interactive nature, social-media represents a crucial communication instrument for MaX community building, which effectively reinforce and tune the MaX image and identity. Among social-media channels different circles are covered by different social platforms. The technical blog (merging the issues covered by the current technical partners blogs) may cover the first (*domain scientists*) and partially the second (*stakeholders*) circles. A more general blog, based on a well-established social platform (as LinkedIn) may cover communication within the second and third (*science interested persons and entrepreneurs*) circles. General communication social platforms as Twitter or Instagram may be effective for their cross circles capability to intercept broad audiences.

Non-media communications

Non-media communications as (i) the organisation and participation in congresses and schools, (ii) the participation at trade sectorial fairs, (iii) meetings with companies, and possibly (iv) the organisation of cultural events (exhibitions, etc.) are particularly operative for promoting both, MaX services and its image. When coupled with social-media communications these non-media-events will act as effective amplifiers of social media coverage

6 Definition of KPIs

MaX-KPIs are intended to be a set of qualitative and quantitative measurable indicators aimed at describing the impact of MaX actions. They are focussed on MaX mission. MaX-KPIs are designed to be easily measurable and will be used to gauge our performance in terms of achievement of our strategic and operational goals.

6.1 KPI segmentation and description

To facilitate MaX-KPIs identification and discussion, we have segmented the action of MaX in three functional areas: (i) Infrastructure and Services, (ii) Software Development, Data

Management & Exascale, (iii) Dissemination, Exploitation, and Management. In the following we discuss the rationale under KPIs' choice for each of the functional areas.

6.1.1 Infrastructure and services

MAX action is centred on services. To be delivered, a service must be included in a catalogue (the Catalogue of Services) and implemented through the infrastructure. The KPIs of this functional area, KPI-1 to KPI-3, are defined as:

KPI-1 INFRASTRUCTURE – Code Maintenance and Availability

KPI-1 measures the maintenance activity and availability of the MaX-Flagship codes by counting the number of public releases of the flagship codes. While three major releases are deliverables of WP1, more releases are expected as a signature of an active community of software users and developers, reporting and fixing bugs, implementing and exploiting new features, and in general maintaining the community codes.

KPI-2 SERVICES – Number of End-Users

KPI-2 measures the total number of users that can profit from MaX e-infrastructure. Users are defined as users of the MaX flagship codes, users of the MaX support services (basic support, help-desk support, consulting in HPC and materials science), users of MaX training and education services (number of attendees of MaX Training and Education initiatives).

KPI-3 SERVICE DEVELOPMENT – Catalogue of services

By counting the number of operated services, KPI-3 monitors activities focused on the development of new services for MaX users.

6.1.2 Software development, data management and exascale

The other relevant pillars of MAX action are software development, ecosystem building, exascale development (including co-design) and exploitation, and data management. The KPIs of this functional area are defined as:

KPI-4 SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT – New implemented features and cross code integration

KPI-4 is designed to measure the large scale activity of MaX software development on community codes in electronic structure and materials science. Among the SW development actions, here we decided to focus on the development of new features (directly impacting the end-users of the codes), as well as on those features especially aimed at modularization and cross code integration, in turn impacting code maintainability and, to a larger extent, the exploitation of MaX development to a wider extent out of the initial community of the flagship codes.

KPI-5 ECOSYSTEM – Impact of the flagship codes

The flagship codes of MaX are legacy community codes in electronic structure and materials science and are part of a common ecosystem active in high-performance and high-throughput calculations. KPI-5 measures the size of the users basin of the MaX software ecosystem, an extremely relevant measure of MaX impact. It is defined as the max among: Number of unique downloads of the flagship codes; Number of journal citations of MaX reference code papers; Number of forum subscribers.

KPI-6 EXASCALE – Codesign

In the roadmap towards exascale, the MaX CoE has planned a number of technical activities, including co-design, aimed at identifying requirements and evaluating design points and solutions in the perspective of the materials science community. All these activities are going to be evaluated through KPI-6 by counting the number of performance measurements done on the flagship codes or on-purpose mini-app (a single performance measurement is intended as a table of data relative to a single app on a single architecture, collected with different run configurations of threads and tasks). It is important to note that the concept of performance is here general, possibly meaning energy to solution, time to solution, system exploitation, etc. depending on the technology/design point under examination.

KPI-7 EXASCALE – HPC Exploitation

MaX is committed to software development in the exascale horizon, with a special emphasis on enabling the computational materials science community to exploit in full the future class of HPC machines. With this in mind, KPI-7 measures the performance of our flagship codes in terms of exploitation of large scale HPC machines. On the basis of selected benchmarks, it will measure the maximum HPC system partition exploited by our codes within a reasonable performance. The reference data will be taken from the performance benchmarks collected for KPI-6.

KPI-8 DATA – Data management

Within the MaX ecosystem both high-performance and high-throughput computing are enabled, implying the need to produce, validate, and store curated data, together with their provenance and full reproducibility. The capability to handle this large amount of information is crucial. In computational materials science, the big issue is not the volume of the computed data but rather their provenance, reproducibility and tracing, which map into databases with complex structures and topologies. As a measure of the materials science data produced by MaX and stored in a public MaX repository, KPI-8 considers the size of the above databases in terms of nodes (as a measure of their complexity).

6.1.3 Dissemination, exploitation, and management

All the above actions will be of no success without effective communication, dissemination and exploitation, to be monitored through three KPIs.

According to MaX philosophy, management is successful when its actions are not directly perceived. Therefore only one KPI is dedicated to this area, measuring the effectiveness of the

process of accumulation and management of the information that forms the MaX knowledge base.

The KPIs of this functional area are relative to these actions are defined as:

KPI-9 DISSEMINATION – Schools, conferences, publications

KPI-9 measures the actions of MaX members for dissemination and training in the broad academic and industrial community. Dissemination through invited presentations (within events organized by MaX or by the HPC and materials community at large), as well as MaX publications, is included. Here by “MaX publications” we mean all scientific papers explicitly acknowledging MaX support or authored by MaX scientists.

KPI-10 DISSEMINATION - Contacts and Visits to industrial entities and Presentations to Industrial Events

KPI-10 measures the dissemination activities towards industries, through an index designed to weigh direct contacts, visits and presentations at industrial events and fairs.

KPI-11 EXPLOITATION – Business Performance

KPI-11 measures the contracts catalysed by MaX, as managed through the appropriate “Engagement” statement.

KPI-12 PROCESS - Knowledge Base Documentation

MaX knowledge base is a crucial asset: KPI-12 measures its documentation, as well as the documentation of best practices, through position papers and reports.

Deliverable D7.2
 First report on setup of CoE governing bodies,
 infrastructure, KPI defs, IPR implementation

6.2 KPI table

	#	Key performance indicator	KPI definition	Type of data required	Start	Target at the End
Infrastructure & Services	1	INFRASTRUCTURE - Codes Maintenance & Availability	Measure of the maintenance activity and availability of the MaX-Flagship codes	Number of public releases of the Flagship Codes	M1	24
	2	SERVICES - Number of End-Users	Number of End-Users taking advantage of the MaX services, including software, support, consulting, education and training.	Number of End-Users for each of the MaX operated services.	M6	1000
	3	SERVICES DEVELOPMENT - Catalogue of Services	Measure the number of Operated Services	Number of services documented on MaX Users Portal that can be activated via SUEP (services activated through different channels, e.g. different email addresses, are considered independent)	M6	10
Software Development, Data Management & Exascale	4	SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT - New implemented features and Cross Code Integration	Measure the new features implemented in the Flagship Codes including those devoted to Cross Code Integration	Number of new features implemented in the Flagship Codes as reported in the development agenda, including the self standing modules (counted one for each code)	M6	20
	5	ECOSYSTEM - Impact of MaX Codes	Measure of impact of the Flagship Codes	MaX among: Number of unique downloads of the flagship codes; Number of journal citations on MaX reference code papers; Number of forum/ mailing list subscribers	M8	2000/y
	6	EXASCALE - Codesign	Number of performance measurements (a single performance measurement is intended as a table of data relative to a single app on a single architecture, collected with different run configurations of threads and tasks)	Performance curves (energy to solution, time to solution, system exploitation)	M8	8
	7	EXASCALE - Exploitation	Maximum HPC system partition exploited (in Pflop/s)	Size of the maximum partition exploited per each code. Reference data will be taken from the performance curves of KPI-6	M8	1,5
	8	DATA - Data Management	Measure of the size of the collected data in the open MaX repository of materials data, workflows, turn-key solutions, and protocols (as defined by D3.5)	Number of Nodes in the AiiDA database graph technically underlying the open MaX repository	M18	10 ⁶
	Dissemination, Exploitation & Management	9	DISSEMINATION - Schools, Conferences, Publications	Participation upon invitation of MaX scientists to Schools and Conferences plus Publications of MaX scientists (either authored or acknowledged)	Total number of invited talks to Conferences and Schools + Total number of publications acknowledging MaX (or given/authored by MaX scientists)	M8
10		DISSEMINATION - Contacts and Visits to industrial entities and Presentations to Industrial Events	Measure the MaX activity on industries	MCI (Max Contact Industry Index) = 1* (Total number of firms contacted by MAX via replied emails or telephone calls) + 10* (Total number of MAX visit to single industrial entities) + 100* (Total number of Presentations to Industrial Events and Sectorial Fairs) as reported by CRM	M8	1000
11		EXPLOITATION - Business Performance	Industry projects promoted by MaX	Total number of contracts disciplined by the "Engagement to Execute a Third Order Party"	M6	30
12		PROCESS - Knowledge Base Documentation/Best Practices	Number of documents defining the MaX knowledge Base and documenting MaX Best Practices	Total number of documents managing the MaX knowledge Base and documenting MaX Best Practices	M6	30

7 IPR implementation

MaX follows the rules for intellectual property set out by the EC, specifically:

- “Background” i.e. partners’ pre-existing know-how, while remaining the sole property of their owners, will be made available to other partners when needed for the project implementation. The background “excluded” will be identified in writing within the “agreement on background” that will be included in the Consortium Agreement.
- “Foreground” i.e. knowledge developed throughout the project, will be owned by the partners who have directly contributed to its creation. In case of joint ownership, a separate contract will be drawn up and signed by the co-owners to determine their rights and obligations, and settle the IP management and exploitation rules.
- Traceability of Background and Foreground will be one part of the data, which will be recorded.

These principles are fully described and agreed within the Consortium Agreement in section 8-10 (see Annex I). The following objects are included:

8.0 Ownership of Results

8.1 Joint Ownership

8.2 Transfer of Results

8.3.1 Dissemination of own Results

8.3.2 Dissemination of another Party’s unpublished Results and Background

8.3.3 Cooperation obligations

8.3.4 Use of names, logos or trademarks

8.4 Exclusive licenses

9. Access Rights

9.1 Background included

9.2 General Principles

9.3 Access Rights for implementation

9.4 Access Rights for Exploitation

9.5 Access for Affiliated Entities

9.6 Additional Access Rights

9.7 Access Rights for Parties entering or leaving the consortium

9.8 Specific Provisions for Access Rights to Software

10. Non-disclosure of information

As specified in the DoA, all MaX codes are developed according to an OSI-recognized Open Source License; in addition to specific software development, the Consortium agreed on making all deliverables public (with a creative commons license), and all the results will be released as open data, facilitating take-up and follow-up research.

Since for some specific commercial activities there may be questions related to licensing (specifically the interaction with open source licenses and IPR of the company requesting

support) it has been decided to add an internal help desk on OSS licensing that will cover most issues related to redistribution, proper dissemination and compliance.

All MaX deliverables and reports are public.

8 Annexes

Annex I Guidelines for engagement to execute third party order

Guidelines for engagement to execute third party order

This document regulates the procedures that will be applied to activities and services that MaX will execute upon request or for the benefit of external entities.

Definitions:

The term “Order” identifies the correlated set of activities and operations aimed at creating products or services corresponding to specific goals, which must be coherent with the general purposes of MaX. Orders are usually activated through a customer’s contract.

The term “Director of the order” identifies the person in charge of managing the execution of the Order. In exceptional cases due to the complexity of the order execution, the management of the Order could be assigned to more than one person. “Small order” identifies an order, which involves a payment and/or an estimated cost of execution below 20.000 (twenty thousand) Euro.

Appointing the Director of the order:

For any single Order to be executed, the MaX Coordinator identifies a Director of the order after informal consultations, according to the procedure and criteria described below. In case of acceptance, the Director of the order shall assume the full responsibility and coordination of the execution of the Order, including the formal signature of the contracts between his/her institution and the customer. Throughout the execution of the Order, he/she will provide reports to the Executive Manager and the MaX Coordinator. He/she will make sure that MaX is duly cited in any formal contract and in any public presentation referring to the Order. The identification of the Director of the order takes into account the following criteria:

- Technical capability for execution
- Availability for execution of the activities in the requested period
- Customer satisfaction in the execution of previous Orders
- A balanced distribution of the Orders among Parties
- The Parties’ contributions to obtaining the Order

In case of an Order directly proposed by a Party, the direction of the Order is assigned by the principal investigator (PI) of that Party and communicated to the MaX Coordinator within 5 days.

The MaX Coordinator will immediately inform all Parties about the appointment of the Director of the order. In case any Party objects within 5 days and no consensus is reached through informal consultations, the MaX Coordinator invites all Parties to vote by email within the next 5 days and the decision is taken according to the majority. If the votes are evenly divided, the vote of the MaX Coordinator is decisive.

The procedure described in the previous paragraph does not apply to Small orders and to Orders directly proposed by a Party.

Any Party who considers that an Order directly proposed by another Party is not appropriate or coherent with the general purposes of MaX may ask for a decision of the General Assembly within 5 days. In this case, the General Assembly will decide whether such Order will be part of MaX activities.

The Coordinator shall ensure that an updated list of all on going Orders is available to all Parties via web, and a summary report of all orders shall be presented at meetings of the General Assembly.

Annex II Consortium Agreement (IPR sections)